

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

*a non-profit
research institute affiliated with
the University of Bergen*

*Edv. Griegsvei 3a,
N-5059 Bergen
Norway*

NERSC Technical Report no. 182
to
Norwegian Space Centre
under contract no. JOP.8.3.3.13.98.2

Applications of Earth Observation Data for Monitoring Algae Blooms in the Coastal Zone

-

WP 5: Indian plans for using satellites for coastal zone monitoring

by

Paul Samuel and Lasse H. Pettersson

Bergen, December, 1999

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Edv. Griegsvei 3a

N-5059 Bergen, NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 29 72 88 Fax: +47 55 20 00 50

e-mail: admin@nrsc.noWebs-site: <http://www.nrsc.no>

*a non-profit environmental research center
affiliated with the University of Bergen*

REPORT

TITLE Applications of Earth Observation Data for Monitoring Algae Blooms in the Coastal Zone – WP 5: Indian plans for using satellites for coastal zone monitoring	REPORT No. Technical report no. 182
CLIENT Norwegian Space Centre	CONTRACT No. JOP.8.3.3.13.98.2
CONTACT PERSONS Guro Dahle Strøm	AVAILABILITY OPEN
AUTHORS Paul Samuel and Lasse H. Pettersson	DATE December, 1999
SUMMARY <p>This document covers the reporting of WP 5 under the above contract with the Norwegian Space Centre. The report covers investigation and a survey of the Indian applications of EO data in the coastal zone. The aim of the report is to identify possible EO applications in India of relevance to relevant developments initiated for the Norwegian Coastal zone.</p>	
APPROVAL Lasse H. Pettersson	 Ola M. Johannessen, Director

Table of Contents

1	CURRENTLY AVAILABLE DATA OF RELEVANCE FOR COASTAL ZONE APPLICATIONS	4
1.1	SATELLITE MISSIONS	4
1.2	SENSORS	5
1.2.1	<i>Linear Imaging Self-scanning Sensor (LISS):</i>	5
1.2.2	<i>Panchromatic Camera (PAN):</i>	5
1.2.3	<i>Wide Field Sensor (WiFS):</i>	5
1.2.4	<i>Multi-spectral Optical Scanner (MOS):</i>	9
1.2.5	<i>Ocean Colour Monitor (OCM):</i>	9
1.2.6	<i>Multifrequency Scanning Microwave Radiometer (MSMR):</i>	9
2	APPLICATIONS	10
2.1	WETLAND MAPPING	10
2.2	CORAL REEF MAPPING	10
2.3	CHANGE DETECTION	10
2.4	PLANT COMMUNITY IDENTIFICATION	10
2.5	COASTAL PROCESSES	10
2.6	COASTAL WATERS	11
3	IRS-P3 MOS VALIDATION EXPERIMENT	11
4	CONCLUSIONS	12
5	REFERENCES	12
6	CONTACTS	13

1 CURRENTLY AVAILABLE EO DATA OF RELEVANCE FOR COASTAL ZONE APPLICATIONS

Remote sensing is an important part of the Indian Space Programme and the Department of Space (DoS) of the Government of India, as the nodal agency for the realisation of several national level application projects such as the National Natural Resources Management System, the National Resources Information System, and the Integrated Mission for Sustainable Development, collaborates closely with user agencies. The major goals of the remote sensing programme in India are: 1) the implementation of indigenous remote sensing satellite programme, 2) continuous build-up of infrastructure for generation of products from various sensor data, 3) demonstration of applications techniques to promote the technology, 4) execution of applications projects for resource monitoring to enable technology transfer to user agencies and 5) imparting training to resource scientists.

1.1 Satellite Missions

Table 1 shows an overview of the Indian satellite missions, which mark important milestones in the Indian Space Programme.

Table 1. Major Indian remote sensing satellites.

Satellite(s)	Launch	Life	Orbit	Mission description	Payload
IRS-1A IRS-1B	Mar '88 Aug '91	4+ years 6+ years	Polar sun-synchronous orbit at 904 km; 22-day repeat	Operational first generation remote sensing; Resource mapping	Linear Imaging Self-scanning Sensors (LISS)
IRS-P2	Oct '94	4+ years	Polar sun-synchronous orbit at 817 km; 24-day repeat	Launched by indigenous vehicle; Resource mapping	Modified LISS
IRS-1C IRS-1D	Dec '95 Oct '97		Polar sun-synchronous orbit at 817 km; 24-day repeat	Operational second generation remote sensing; Resource mapping	Panchromatic (PAN) Camera; LISS-III; Wide Field Sensor (WiFS)
IRS-P3	Apr '96		Polar sun-synchronous orbit at 817 km; 24-day repeat	Launched by indigenous vehicle; Resource mapping; X-ray astronomy; Oceanography	WiFS; Modular Opto-electronic Sensor (MOS)
IRS-P4 (OCEAN SAT-1)	'99		Polar sun-synchronous orbit at 720 km; 2-day repeat	Oceanography	Ocean Colour Monitor (OCM); Multi-frequency Scanning Microwave Radiometer (MSMR)
IRS-P5 (CARTO SAT)	'99		Polar sun-synchronous orbit at 617.99 km 5-day repeat	Cartography & Terrain mapping	2 PAN Cameras
IRS-P6 (RESOUR SAT)	2000			Agriculture & Forestry	LISS-IV; LISS-III; WiFS

1.2 Sensors

Since the Indian satellite missions to-date have been aimed primarily at land applications such as the mapping of natural resources, land-use, forest-cover, water resources, terrain, etc., most of the data provided by the sensors have not been particularly useful for oceanographic applications. Nevertheless, IRS-P3 carries a sensor specially designed for ocean colour studies, namely, the Modular Opto-Electronic Scanner (MOS). In addition, the Wide Field Sensor (WiFS) carried by the IRS-1C, IRS-1D and IRS-P3 satellites have also been used to study aspects of importance to coastal management, such as shoreline changes, sediment transport, mangroves, etc. Other sensors such as LISS-III, SWIR and PAN have found applications in areas such as discrimination of coastal vegetation types, siting of coastal structures and inventories of coastal landuse.

With the planned launch in early 1999 of the IRS-P4, or OCEANSAT-1, India will have a mission dedicated to oceanographic applications. This will carry two sensors, the Ocean Colour Monitor (OCM) and the Multi-frequency Scanning Microwave Radiometer (MSMR). These sensors are designed to extract coastal ocean parameters such as chlorophyll concentration, sea surface temperature and surface wind speed. Important characteristics of the relevant sensors for coastal studies are tabulated in Table 2. The important sensors for coastal and ocean applications are described below:

1.2.1 Linear Imaging Self-scanning Sensor (LISS):

IRS-1A & B each carried one LISS I camera with a resolution of 72.5 m and a swath of 148 km, and two LISS II cameras with a resolution of 36.25 m and a composite swath of 145 km. These are advanced imaging sensors operating in the push broom mode and provides data in four spectral bands, three in the visible and one in the near infra-red. For the IRS-P2, an improved LISS-II camera was used which covers the same 4 spectral bands and a swath of 130 km with a resolution of 37.39 m along track and 32.74 m across track. IRS-1C & D carry LISS-III cameras have 4 spectral bands, but one of the visible bands has been replaced by one in the middle infra-red. LISS data have been extensively used for mapping coastal geomorphology, land use, vegetation, chlorophyll, coral reefs, mangroves, etc.

1.2.2 Panchromatic Camera (PAN):

PAN was flown on IRS-1C & D and provides high resolution (5.2 - 5.8 m) data in the visible region along a swath of 63 - 70 km. PAN has the advantage that it is steerable to within ± 26 deg (± 398 km) off nadir, thereby improving the revisit time to 3 days. PAN data have been used in applications such as mapping coastal land use, geomorphology, coral reefs, siting of coastal structures, shoreline changes, etc.

1.2.3 Wide Field Sensor (WiFS):

WiFS is a coarse resolution camera operating in push broom scanning mode using a linear array of Charge Coupled Devices (CCDs) as sensors. These devices fly on the IRS-1C, IRS-1D and IRS-P2 satellites. Two spectral bands (B3 and B4, same as LISS bands 3 and 4) are available with an additional middle infra-red band (B5, same as LISS-III band 5) on the IRS-P3 WiFS. It has a wide swath in the range 728 - 812 km, which results in a revisit time of 5 days notwithstanding the satellites' nominal 24-day repeat cycles. The spectral bands chosen for WiFS are primarily meant for vegetation dynamics studies and have been used for monitoring mangroves and coastal land use. However, WiFS data have

also been useful for monitoring sediment dynamics in the coastal ocean as well as for mapping coastal geomorphology and shoreline changes.

Table 2. Overview of sensors useful for coastal and ocean studies.

Sensor name & Acronym	Satellite	Swath (km)	Spatial Resolution (m)	Revisit time (days)	Spectral Bands (μ) / Frequencies (GHz)	Applications	Reference
Linear Imaging Self-scanning Sensor (LISS-III)	IRS-1A IRS-1B IRS-1C IRS-1D IRS-P2	131 - 148	23 - 72	22	1 : 0.45 - 0.52 2 : 0.52 - 0.59 3 : 0.62 - 0.68 4 : 0.77 - 0.86 5 : 1.55 - 1.70	Chlorophyll Coral reefs Mangroves Shoreline change Coastal land use Coastal geomorphology	
Panchromatic Camera (PAN)	IRS-1C IRS-1D	70	5.8	3 - 24	0.50 - 0.75	Coastal land use Coral reefs Shoreline change Coastal geomorphology	
Wide Field Sensor (WIFS)	IRS-1C IRS-1D IRS-P3	728 - 812	188 - 246	5 - 24	B3 : 0.62 - 0.68 B4 : 0.77 - 0.86 B5 : 1.55 - 1.69	Mangroves Shoreline change Coastal land use Coastal geomorphology Sediment dynamics	

Sensor name & Acronym	Satellite	Swath (km)	Spatial Resolution (m)	Revisit time (days)	Spectral Bands (μ) / Frequencies (GHz)	Applications	Reference
Modular Optoelectronic Scanner (MOS-AB/C)	IRS-P3		523 - 2500	24	0.755 – 0.758	Pigments Chlorophyll Algal blooms Sediment dynamics	
					0.759 – 0.762		
					0.762 – 0.765		
					0.765 - 0.768		
					0.398 – 0.418		
					0.434 – 0.454		
					0.475 – 0.495		
					0.511 – 0.531		
					0.561 – 0.581		
					0.605 – 0.625		
					0.640 – 0.660		
					0.675 – 0.695		
					0.740 – 0.760		
0.858 - 0.878							
1.001- 1.021							
0.804 – 0.824							
0.933 – 0.953							
1.500 – 1.700							
Ocean Colour Monitor (OCM)	IRS-P4 (OCEANSAT-1)	1420	236 - 360	2	0.402 – 0.422	Pigments Chlorophyll Algal blooms Coastal water types Sediment dynamics Ocean dynamics	
					0.433 – 0.453		
					0.480 – 0.500		
Multifrequency Scanning Microwave Radiometer (MSMR)	IRS-P4 (OCEANSAT-1)	1420	120	2	6.60- GHz	Sea surface temperature Surface wind speed	
			75		10.65 GHz		
			45		18.70 GHz		
			40		21.30 GHz		

1.2.4 Multi-spectral Optical Scanner (MOS):

MOS, which flies on the IRS-P3, was developed by DLR, Germany primarily for chlorophyll mapping, biomass monitoring, coastal water discrimination, sediment dynamics and ocean dynamics. It is a multispectral imaging spectrometer operating in narrow spectral bands in the visible, near infra-red and middle infra-red regions of the spectrum. It has bands specifically for enabling accurate modelling of atmospheric effects in the radiance measurements and uses 16-bit quantisation for the radiance to ensure high sensitivity. MOS consists of three optical modules, namely, MOS-A, MOS-B and MOS-C, operating in the different spectral regions and with differing resolutions and swath widths.

1.2.5 Ocean Colour Monitor (OCM):

The OCM, which will be flown on the IRS-P4 (OCEANSAT-1) will have 8 spectral bands in the visible and near infra-red region, corresponding to those of SeaWiFS. The data provided will be optimal for quantitative estimation of Chlorophyll concentration. The OCM will have a resolution of 360 m x 236 m, which will enable good resolution of the coastal distribution. It will have a wide swath of 1420 KM, ensuring frequent revisits.

1.2.6 Multifrequency Scanning Microwave Radiometer (MSMR):

This is a multifrequency, dual polarised microwave radiometer to be flown on the IRS-P4. The system has been configured with scanning mechanism in order to collect data at a constant incidence angle of 50 deg over the entire 1420 km swath. The MSMR will be useful for retrieving parameters such as sea surface temperature, wind speed over the oceans and total precipitable atmospheric water vapour content.

2 APPLICATIONS

The major areas in which remote sensing application projects are conducted in India are: 1) water resources, 2) land use 3) geosciences 4) agriculture and soils 5) forestry 6) oceanography 7) integrated surveys. The applications IRS data in the Indian coastal zone have tended to focus on studies related to the mapping and monitoring of wetland conditions and changes, coral reef areas, mangroves, coastal landforms, submerged bars and underwater features, shoreline changes, suspended sediment dynamics, coastal currents, ocean dumping and oil pollution.

2.1 Wetland mapping

Remote sensing data provide information about the areal extent, condition and boundaries of the wetlands. IRS LISS-I and II data have been extensively used for wetland mapping along the Indian coast. It has been possible to distinguish between mangroves and seaweed and to categorise wetlands into beach, mudflat and mangrove as well as on the basis of density.

2.2 Coral reef mapping

Coral reef maps of several sections of the Indian coastal waters have been prepared using IRS LISS data. Features such as the type, the mud and sand over the reef, coralline shelf, reef vegetation, sand/beach vegetation, algae, seagrass, seaweeds, type of lagoonal bottom, live corals and the high and low waterlines have been mapped.

2.3 Change detection

The revisit times (20+ days) and the length of the time series (since 1972) for the IRS data are well-suited for monitoring seasonal and long-term changes in wetland conditions. Data have been particularly useful for detecting changes in mangrove and coral reef areas.

2.4 Plant community identification

Various digital enhancement techniques have been used to identify different plant communities. Band ratio combinations of red/green, red/infra-red and near infra-red/red, and principal component analysis were found to be most suitable for classifying vegetation types in wetlands. The combination of band red, vegetation index and infra-red also helps in distinguishing between mangroves, swamps and other vegetation in the wetland zone. LISS II's poorer radiometric resolution as compared to that of Landsat TM, makes it slightly less effective for these type of studies.

2.5 Coastal processes

Coastal processes of erosion, deposition, sediment transport, flooding and sea level affect features such as shoreline changes, coastal landforms, tidal boundaries and offshore bars and underwater features. IRS data are yet to prove their usefulness for such studies owing to the poor spatial resolution. However, they are useful for large area sediment transport studies and in detecting long-term changes in the coastline.

2.6 Coastal waters

Turbidity/suspended sediments and colour/chlorophyll are indicators of coastal water quality which are observable from satellite data. The best wavelengths for observing suspended sediments are in the range 0.550 μ to 0.650 μ as shorter wavelengths introduce atmospheric noise while longer do not penetrate deeper than the upper few centimeters of water. This band is present in LISS, PAN, WiFS, MOS and OCM data. Several investigations have been conducted to map the suspended sediment distributions over sections of the Indian coastal waters. Some attempts have also been made to map primary productivity and chlorophyll in coastal waters from LISS-II data, although the spectral channels and bandwidths are not optimal for this purpose.

3 IRS-P3 MOS VALIDATION EXPERIMENT

A dedicated validation experiment was co-ordinated in 1996 –'98 by the Space Applications Centre, Ahmedabad with participation by 7 other institutes from all over the country. The objective of this experiment was to evaluate IRS-P3 MOS-B data for retrieval of ocean parameters against sea truth data collected along the satellite underpasses. The main tasks included the collection and analysis of sea truth data relating to bio-geochemical, surface and atmospheric measurements, development and validation of algorithms for parameter retrieval and estimation of chlorophyll-a, suspended sediment concentration and yellow substance for case I and case II waters using MOS-B data. The main results from this study are listed below:

- i. The sun glitter effect was modelled and eliminated, making oceanic features more prominent.
- ii. Algorithm for atmospheric correction was developed.
- iii. Ocean parameters chlorophyll, suspended sediment, yellow substance and aerosol optical depths were computed using a principal component inversion model, after eliminating sun glitter effect. Time series were generated for Goa coast in India and a scene from the Adriatic Sea was also analysed..
- iv. Three ocean colour algorithms (single ratio based model, degraded product model and three component model) were derived using the in situ data
- v. About 26 different bio-optical algorithms were evaluated. The OC2 algorithm was found to be the best as it gave best results for high and low chlorophyll concentrations.
- vi. A preliminary analysis was carried out to integrate MOS-B chlorophyll data and AVHRR sea surface temperature using clustering techniques
- vii. Seasonal variations in chlorophyll content in the Arabian Sea was analysed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

While data from the Indian satellites have been put to many applications over land areas including coastal areas, currently only MOS-B data appear to be useful for the kind of applications envisaged in the current study, namely monitoring of algal blooms. The choice of bandwidths and the quantisation levels used for the other sensors make the data unsuited for ocean colour studies. There is very little information available on the use of satellite data to monitor algal blooms in the Indian coastal waters, possibly because it is not perceived as a major issue. However, MOS-B data should be suited for such applications due to its narrow spectral bands in the relevant range.

5 REFERENCES

- Nayak, S. and B. Manikiam, *IRS-1A Applications for Coastal Zone Management*. In *Natural Resources Management – A New Perspective*, National Natural Resources Management System, Bangalore, India.
- NRSA Data Centre, 1995. *Satellite Data Products Source Book*. NRSA Data Centre, Hyderabad, India.
- NRSA Data Centre, 1998. *Satellite Data Products from NRSA Data Centre (NDC)*. NRSA Data Centre, Hyderabad, India.
- NRSA Data Centre, 1997. *IRS-1D Handbook*. National Remote Sensing Agency, Hyderabad, India.
- Task Team: IRS P3 – Ocean Applications, 1998. *IRS P3 Validation Experiment : Ocean Applications*. Space Applications Centre (ISRO), Ahmedabad, India.
- Nayak, S., 1996. *Monitoring the Coastal Environment of India Using Satellite Data*. Frank Cass Journals, Science, Technology and Development, Frank Cass, London.

6 CONTACTS

1. **Dr. Shailesh Nayak**, Head, Marine and Water Resources Division, RESA,
Space Applications Centre (Indian Space Research Organisation, Dept. of Space,
Govt. of India),
SAC P.O., Ahmedabad 380 053 INDIA
Tel: +91 (79) 447 043 / 445 002 / 446 099 / 440 260 / 642 3967
Fax: +91 (79) 674 7708 / 656 1410 / 656 8556 / 656 8073

2. **Mr. Joseph Arokiadas**, Head, / Mr. K.P.R. Menon
NRSA Data Centre,
National Remote Sensing Agency
Balanagar, Hyderabad 500 037 INDIA
Tel: +91 (40) 307 8560 / 307 9572 Ext. 2318
Fax: +91 (40) 307 8664 / 307 8648

3. **Dr. B.R. Subramanian**, Project Director
Integrated Coastal and Marine Area Management Project Directorate
Dept. of Ocean Development, Govt. of India
Koodal Bldg., Anna University Campus
Chennai 600 025 INDIA
Tel: +91 (44) 230 1845
Fax: +91 (44) 230 1846
E-mail: icmam@tn.nic.in

4. **Prof. Dr. S. Ramachandran**, Director
Institute for Ocean Management
Koodal Bldg., Anna University Campus
Chennai 600 025 INDIA
Tel: +91 (44) 235 3312 Direct) / 235 1723 Ext. 3290
Fax: +91 (44) 235 3312 / 230 1846